

Open Humanities Manifesto – an advocacy case for humanities in the Open Science era

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Abstract. This poster will present the Open Humanities Manifesto as the initial salvo of a bold advocacy project geared towards making open humanities more sustainable. It also aims to discuss the need to put more effort into practising advocacy by researchers, science managers, editors, and librarians, and argue for scaling up the OHM as an advocacy tool in the international context. By contributing to the conversation on advancing research assessment in the spirit of open science, the poster closely aligns with the goals of the GraspOS 2025 conference.

Conference Themes: Open Infrastructures for Responsible Research
Assessment, Recognition of Contributions to Open Science

Keywords: Research Assessment Reform, Advocacy, Open Science

1 Main Contribution

“The humanities are at the forefront of open science. The free flow of thought and ideas is at its core and should be the default way to share knowledge.” – the creators of the Open Humanities Manifesto (OHM, see the original in Polish here [1]) wrote in the summer of 2024. The document, created in collaboration with a diverse group of stakeholders in the field of the humanities in Poland – researchers, librarians, and publishers – had one specific goal: to draw the public and policy attention to the needs of that field in the era of digital and open practices. Among the over 200 signatories of the Manifesto are researchers at various career stages, publishers, editors, librarians, and representatives of the cultural sector, as well as institutions: RPOs, NGOs, learned societies, and university departments.

The OHM draws attention to the ongoing evolution of scholarly communication practices, driven by digital scholarship and open science, which are becoming the default approaches to research and steering the field's development (see, for example, the Vienna Digital Humanism Manifesto [2]). These approaches yield many innovations across the entire spectrum of scholarly activities, from research design (open methods), through data capture (FAIR and open data), to dissemination of

results (open access). Yet, such practices are not adequately recognised in research assessment.

In response, OHM, echoing landmark initiatives such as Plan S [3], CoARA [4], DORA [5], and the Helsinki Initiative on Multilingualism [6], introduces four core postulates to set an agenda for research assessment reform in Poland:

1. The evaluation system should acknowledge and support the practices of open science.
2. The evaluation of achievements should consider the diversity of research outputs specific to the humanities.
3. Open publishing models should be supported and sustained.
4. The development and internationalisation of the humanities require strengthening the national infrastructure of open science.

The poster will present OHM as the initial phase of a strategic advocacy project aimed at strengthening the sustainability of open humanities. It situates the manifesto within the broader landscape of international initiatives, including the work of OPERAS, and national open science policies. By reflecting on these examples, the poster highlights how advocacy tools like OHM can be adapted to diverse institutional contexts—from research-performing organisations and university libraries to cultural heritage institutions—fostering dialogue and knowledge exchange across the sector.

Ultimately, the OHM serves as both a practical advocacy instrument and a conceptual framework for advancing inclusive, context-sensitive, and digitally enabled research assessment. By scaling such initiatives internationally and fostering synergies with ongoing Open Science reforms, OHM contributes to shaping sustainable, open, and innovative practices within the humanities.

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